

USER MANUAL

1. This creative workshop is intended for educational, non-commercial purposes only. The developers cannot guarantee that any learning will occur over the course of the workshop.
2. Workshop facilitators should avail of this USER MANUAL, the attached printable worksheet and the authorised slide deck.
3. Having at least two groups engaging in the workshop is optimal: one each of Marketing Mavens® and Legal Eagles®. This document will instruct you how to facilitate the workshop over ca. 90 minutes. Facilitators may experiment with other group compositions and scheduling at their own risk.
4. The slide deck is intended to transmit the core ideas of the workshop directly into participants' brains and accustom them to the demands of their membership of Marketing Mavens® and Legal Eagles®. It is expected that the presentation can be delivered in 7-10 minutes.

5. Begin by introducing the language used to describe edtech. Focus on the vagueness of the claims, developers' ability to describe the products however they want, and their power to shape classroom realities by enforcing their preferred terms of service.
6. The following slides provide examples of marketing strategies relying on 1) the active and appealing but meaningless language used to sell edtech products; 2) the bogus and questionable metrics and standards; 3) the purported friendliness and good intentions of the companies and their products.
7. Your discussion of the marketing language should seamlessly transition to an overview of language used to define the terms of service, privacy policies and other legal and law-adjacent aspects of the technology.
8. Begin by pointing out how the language shifts as compliance documents become much wordier than marketing artefacts. They are still ambiguous but in a manner that is distinct from the vagueness of marketing. Demonstrate companies' reliance on plausible-looking, if made-up or self-certified, badges and standards to convince users of the products' adherence to best practices.
9. Show that tech companies themselves admit that nobody reads their legal documents, and the documents provide more questions than answers. Who are the third parties? What does "a broad range of services" mean?
10. Make note of the fact that while the companies are vague and non-committal when describing what their users can expect from them, they expect users to strictly follow the terms of service and other requirements. Schools and universities are in turn required to create their own compliance documents.
11. Point out the difference between digital and earlier technologies. The latter are rarely marketed and are never accompanied by terms of service and privacy policies. This introduces the key idea of the workshop: **why should digital technologies be special? What would happen if we applied the same language and expectations to familiar classroom tools? The aim is to unsettle ideas of the digital and of digital learning that are implicit in educational discourses by paying closer attention to the language we use.**

ESSAY

WORD CLOUD

STICKY NOTE

STONE TABLET

BLACKBOARD

MCQ

CAVE PAINTING

ORAL

12. Highlight the promises (once) held by familiar objects used by educators. The first teacher to use a post-it note in their classroom certainly deserved an innovation award. How much sharpening time has been saved by the introduction of the mechanical pencil? You are encouraged to come up with your own examples, but the workshop developers cannot vouch for their effectiveness.
13. Mention that familiar classroom objects also come with their rules and requirements. Nobody needs a legal document outlining which objects can be safely cut with scissors. We do not define the angle and velocity at which a students' movement can be penalised as chair rocking. But we all internalise and follow these rules.
14. The workshop asks participants to make these promises and rules explicit by developing marketing and compliance strategies for familiar classroom objects, as demonstrated by the included examples of the EcoSit chair and the Scissors Inc. Cutting Utensil.
15. Divide your group into teams. In the first half of the workshop, they will embody the personas of the Marketing Mavens® and later work as the Legal Eagles®. Give each group a worksheet, which can be printed on 2 sheets of A3 paper, with a cutout for the product visualisation in the middle. Provide pens, crayons, scissors, glue and any crafts materials you think may be useful. The worksheet file contains instructions on how to assemble the worksheet with the help of a moderate amount of glue.
16. Over the next 30 minutes, ask the teams to identify a familiar classroom object and create a marketing or compliance strategy using the worksheet. The ideas of the Big Sell, as well as the sample questions included in the slide deck may be used to facilitate their work. Consider giving some examples of familiar classroom objects, such as those included in the slide deck.

17. Encourage doodling within the designated area in the centre of the worksheet, as well as the invention of wholly-made-up though authentic-looking standards, metrics and badges. Big Sell marketing slogans and Small Print disclaimers should be used, though we also suggest relying on bullet points for brevity.

18. After this initial creative activity, have each team present their product and the associated marketing or compliance strategy. Embody the persona of an intrepid investor listening to short (ca. 60 seconds) pitches in a dragons' den-style showcase.
19. Announce that the teams will now work as Legal Eagles. While we expect that the products marketed in the first half of the exercise will be highly successful, participants should engage in compliance activities to ensure that the company developing the products is not liable for any adverse effects resulting from inappropriate use. Ask participants to swap worksheets with another team to facilitate constructive criticism. Make sure that they engage with a different type of product than during the first activity (e.g., if two teams marketed a blackboard). Give them 20 minutes to develop brief terms of service and compliance messages. Encourage teams to build off the other group's doodles and ideas.
20. Facilitate a second round of pitches. It can be shorter than the first one as teams no longer need to introduce their products.

**Marketing
MAVENS**

BIRDS EYE VIEW

LEG X — X LEG

SAFE
| ZONE |

LEG X — X LEG

**LEGAL
EAGLES**

- ★ Every child should have their place in the classroom
- ★ Available in many sizes and colours for a customizable sitting experience
- ★ Fully biodegradable

**ULTIMO
CHAIR**
FROM
ecoSIT

For a more comfortable personal experience

- ⚠ To maintain safety, all four legs of the EcoSit chair should touch the floor while the product is in operation.
- ⚠ The EcoSit chair comes unassembled. The manufacturer does not assume responsibility resulting from incorrect assembly.
- ⚠ All wood used to manufacture the EcoSit chair comes from sustainable Amazon rainforest logging.

Badges of Approval

Warnings of non-compliance

21. Wrap up the activity by reflecting on what this workshop may have achieved. Comment on the implications this exercise may have for educational practices. Ask the participants whether their attitudes to the language of edtech have changed in any way. Do whatever you want, really, as long as you do not hold the workshop developers accountable for the consequences of your actions.
22. If your participants agree, send their creations to workshop developers at michal.wieczorek@ucd.ie and eamon.costello@dcu.ie. Consider giving credit to Dr Michał Wieczorek (University College Dublin), Dr Eamon Costello (Dublin City University), and the project's Chief Doodling Officer, Bryan Mathers of Visual Thinkery.

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23. Michals and Eamons can sometimes make mistakes and give incorrect or even frivolous information. Please verify the content of all the above points independently against original sources and/or a mature adult.
24. See Further Readings below to help use these ideas with students in a course or assessment.

Further Readings

Arvidsson, Adam. "Brands: A Critical Perspective." *Journal of Consumer Culture* 5, no. 2 (2005): 235–58. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469540505053093>.

Bender, Emily M., and Alex Hanna. *The AI Con: How to Fight Big Tech's Hype and Create the Future We Want*. HarperCollins, 2025.

Cone, Lucas, Hanne Knudsen, and Lisa Rosén Rasmussen. "Affective Philanthropy and the Im/Possibility of Governance: The LEGO Foundation's Involvement in Public Education." *Journal of Education Policy* (2026): 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2026.2647074>.

Costello, Eamon, and Stephen Gow. "Authoritarian EdTech." *Dialogues on Digital Society* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1177/29768640251377165>.

Duarte, Tania, Ismael Kherroubi Garcia, Anshur Ramla, Humfress Harriett, Orchard Dylan, and Steph Wright. *Resisting, Refusing, Reclaiming, Reimagining: Charting Challenges to Narratives of AI Inevitability*. Zenodo (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17343830>.

Keegan, John., & Jesse Woo. "How to quickly get to the important truth inside any privacy policy." *The Markup* (2023). <https://themarkup.org/the-breakdown/2023/08/03/how-to-quickly-get-to-the-important-truth-inside-any-privacy-policy>

Kerssens, Niels, T. Philip Nichols, and Luci Pangrazio. "Googlization(s) of Education: Intermediary Work Brokering Platform Dependence in Three National School Systems." *Learning, Media and Technology* 49, no. 3 (2024): 478–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2023.2258339>.

McGarr, Oliver. "The Corporate Branding of Schools in Ireland: Why the Absence of a Critical Debate?" *Irish Educational Studies* (2026): 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2026.2614090>.

Morgan, Glenda. "Success Porn in EdTech: Exaggerating reality, declaring success, and promoting endlessly." *On EdTech Newsletter* (2023). <https://onedtech.philhillaa.com/p/success-porn-in-edtech>

Ortegón, Carlos, Ben Williamson, and Mathias Decuypere. "Edtech Brokers and Evidence Governance: Knowledge Intermediaries in the Education Technology Market." *Globalisation, Societies and Education* (2024): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2024.2439419>.

Rahm, Lina. "'Help!?' My Students Created an Evil AI': On the Irony of Speculative Methods and Design Fiction." *Learning, Media and Technology* (2024): 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2024.2367707>.

Selwyn, Neil. "Minding Our Language: Why Education and Technology Is Full of Bullshit ... and What Might Be Done about It." *Learning, Media and Technology* 41, no. 3 (2016): 437–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2015.1012523>.

Teräs, Marko, Juha Suoranta, Hanna Teräs, and Mark Curcher. "Post-Covid-19 Education and Education Technology 'Solutionism': A Seller's Market." *Postdigital Science and Education* 2, no. 3 (2020): 863–78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-020-00164-x>.

Wieczorek, Michał, and Alberto Romele. "How to Imagine Educational AI: The Filling of a Pail or the Lighting of a Fire?" *Educational Theory* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1111/edth.70070>.

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Wieczorek, M., & Costello, E. (2026). Click Here if You Agree (to Reclaim the EdTech Classroom through Speculative Co-Design). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20538722>

All the drawings have been created by Bryan Mathers of VisualThinkery: <https://visualthinkery.com>

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